

BOOTSTRAP AND JACKKNIFE RESAMPLING: A METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH TO ESTIMATE MAJOR FRUIT CROPS IN NAGALAND

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ABSTRACT

A survey was conducted in all the 12 district of Nagaland; bootstrap and jackknife resampling is adopted to assess the accuracy of the estimation of area and production of major fruit crops with 2200 respondents to be cultivated as major fruit crops. For the majority of fruit growers, a lack of sufficient machinery and tools was regarded as a major impediment, accounting for 66.95 per cent of respondents. For CV estimation of fruit crop production and bearing fruit trees, the results of using the bootstrap and jackknife resampling methods from the original data set demonstrate a significant increase in accuracy.

Key words Bootstrap, jackknife resampling, fruit, non-bearing trees

INTRODUCTION

Horticultural crops, primarily fruits and vegetables, make for around 90.00 per cent of the country's total horticulture production with 8.00 per cent of the total cultivable land with a production of 311.7 mt/year in 2017-18 with fruit accounting for 97.35 mt from 6.50 mh area. India is currently the world's second greatest producer of fruits and vegetables. (Anon. 2020a).

Horticulture in the north east is noted for its massive resources, as well as its diverse climate, altitude and edaphic conditions, which provide enormous opportunities to enrich biodiversity and social diversification in the region. It is a growing industry that has shown to be the finest land-use diversification option for farmers due to the guaranteed and remunerative returns. Horticulture has a higher unit of productivity and offers a lot of room for value addition and its gaining traction across the region, thanks to the region's vast diversity of both indigenous and introduced horticultural crops. The diverse agro-climatic condition has benefitted this region to grow horticulture crops ranging from tropical to temperate crops. The tropical, sub-tropical and temperate fruits include Mandarin Orange, pineapple, Banana, Guava, pears, plum etc. In North east region, the production of fruits accounts to 4867 mt (Nomita and Kavita, 2020). Therefore, the north east region has the great scope for the enhancement of production and productivity under horticulture industry due to conducive climate condition thus improving the socio-economic condition of the farmers of north east region of India.

In 1963, Nagaland was created from the Naga Hills districts of Assam and the North Eastern Frontier Agency province. According to the 2020 census, the state has a population of 19.79 lakh people and covers an area of 16.80 thousand square kilometres. (Anon. 2020b). The population density is low, at 120 people per square kilometre. The rural population makes up 82.26 per cent of the total, while the urban population makes up 17.74 per cent, respectively. The state's diversified agro-climatic conditions, diverse soil types, and adequate rainfall allow for the production of a variety of fruits. The state's geographical location provides enormous potential for horticulture growth. Sub-tropical fruits like pineapple, guava, citrus, and banana, as well as temperate fruits like plum, peach, kiwi, pear, passion fruit, and various nuts, have possibilities for exploitation depending on elevation. Horticultural crops are planted in 104550 ha in Nagaland. Overall horticulture production was 1063960 metric tonnes per year in 2017-18, with this fruit accounting for 380300 tonnes from a 39,320 ha area (Anon. 2021).

Resampling approaches are becoming more popular as statistical tools because they are (typically) quite resilient, their simplicity is appealing, and their computing demands are (mostly) no longer a problem. Scraping or scrambling the original data on a regular basis is one of these ways. They offer a large selection of products, all of which are simple and straightforward to use, and they were first presented in the 1930s (Efron, 1979). However, with the progress of computer technology in recent decades, there has been a significant advancement in the field of resampling. It took a long for these current statistical approaches to emerge, which are computer-intensive, precise, and have a wide range of applications with two specific objectives viz; i). To estimate area and production of major fruit crops in Nagaland, and ii). To perform bootstrap and jackknife resampling to assess the accuracy of the estimate.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

For estimation of area and production of major fruit crops of Nagaland, descriptive research design was used with interview schedule and description or information on relevant parameters collected were analysis and interpreted. Also, accuracy of the estimates was studied using appropriate statistical tools like bootstrapping and jackknife resampling techniques. The research study was conducted in all the 12 districts of Nagaland namely Dimapur, Kiphire, Kohima, Longleng, Mokokchung, Mon, Peren, Phek, Tuensang, Wokha, Noklak and Zunheboto. The secondary data was collected from concerned department, relevant websites about the area, production and the major constraints faced by the horticultural farmers of the state. The primary data on area, yield and other parameters was collected from existing database of horticultural fruit crop growers. By using structured interview schedule on existing sample respondents who were part of the survey conducted by Anon. 2015, information was collected. The survey was based on Probability Proportional to Size-With Repetition (PPSWR) sampling scheme (Alam et al. 2015). Thereby, altogether 20 blocks with 93 villages comprising about 2200 horticultural fruit crop growers of the state was sampled and collected data on area (ha), yield (tons per ha), number of bearing trees and number of non-bearing trees.

Parameters: Socio economic profile of fruit growers, Area (ha) under major fruit crops, Yield (tonne per ha), Number of bearing and non-bearing trees.

Statistical analytical tools

To estimate area and production of major fruit crops in Nagaland adopted from (Efron 1990). Bootstrapping is a method for estimating the sampling distribution of an estimator by resampling with replacement from the original sample. Its procedure is a means of estimating the statistical accuracy from the data in a single sample. It is used to mimic the process of selecting many samples when the population is too small. The samples are generated from the data in the original sample by copying it many numbers of times (Monte Carlo Simulation). Samples then select at random and descriptive statistics was calculated. The results generated from the bootstrap samples were treated as result of actual sampling from the original population adopted from Lahiri (2003), for confidence intervals adopted from Rao, Wu, and Yue (1992). For generating Jack-knife samples and replications adopted from Hendi (2017); The jackknife was originally developed by Quenouille (1949); Tukey (1958) for a non-parametric way to estimate and reduce the bias of an estimator of a population parameter for considerable effort has gone into verifying, and in some cases diversifying, the usefulness of as an estimate of var. Even for the Jackknife Confidence Intervals adopted from Hendi (2017). The collected data will be analysed by using statistical package R 2.15.2. (Ihaka and Gentleman 1996).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. To estimate area and production of major fruit crops

1. Orange

Table 1 reveals the orange cultivation 22.477 ha with total plants 250530, total production of 1152.29 tons in Kohima. Mokokchung with orange production in 965.693 ha with state's largest area and second highest yield, total plants 1029470 and yield 27078.03 tons. Around 16.038 ha of land in Tuensang were planted, producing 817.67 tons from total 32450 plants. 17.021 ha of land in Noklak were planted, producing 1420.34 tons from total 46020 plants. Mon had 162.029 ha of land with production 20485.18 tons with trees of 3023880; Wokha is second largest area 417.603 ha with highest production 36422.53 tons, 1966920 trees in 226.828 ha with yield 10549.36 tons with total of 1066140 trees present. In Phek 258.620 ha with production 18050.65 tons with plants 1272750 comprising bearing and non-bearing. Around 375.119 ha in Dimapur with 384950 plants with 461.04 tons production; 5094.46 ton in Kiphire an area 115.542 ha with 136920 plant, 55.443 ha yielded 5968.88 tons with total trees 593360. Peren 202.10 tons in area 35.425 ha with 120980 plants, while Nagaland produced 127702.53 tons of orange in area 26678.53 ha (Miller 1974).

Table 1. Orange Area, Production and Number of trees

SN	Orange	No. of Bearing trees ('000)	No. of Non - Bearing trees ('000)	Area (ha)	Yield (ton)	No. of Minor trees ('000)
1.	Kohima	132.92	117.61	22.477	1152.30	1.47
2.	Mokokchung	643.01	386.46	965.693	27078.03	16.55
3.	Tuensang	18.22	14.25	16.038	817.67	4.67
4.	Noklak	32.57	13.45	17.021	1420.34	3.16
5.	Mon	1884.91	1138.97	162.029	20485.18	29.50
6.	Wokha	1119.93	846.99	417.603	36422.53	38.88
7.	Zunheboto	528.58	537.56	226.828	10549.36	12.01
8.	Phek	682.74	590.01	258.620	18050.65	10.57
9.	Dimapur	214.06	170.89	375.119	461.04	6.08
10.	Kiphire	85.76	51.16	115.542	5094.46	1.30
11.	Longleng	333.18	260.18	55.443	5968.88	10.61
12.	Peren	63.60	57.38	35.425	202.10	0.61
Nagaland		5739.49	4184.91	2667.83	127702.53	135.43

2. Papaya**Table 2. Papaya Area, Production and Number of trees**

SN	Papaya	No. of Bearing trees ('000)	No. of Non - Bearing trees ('000)	Area (ha)	Yield ('000 unit)	No. of Minor trees ('000)
1.	Kohima	52.07	31.64	6.153	452.44	2.61
2.	Mokokchung	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
3.	Tuensang	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
4.	Noklak	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
5.	Mon	43.80	59.51	17.408	122.97	2.28
6.	Wokha	31.75	48.63	13.466	99.51	1.65
7.	Zunheboto	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
8.	Phek	0.62	0.08	0.039	3.12	0.00
9.	Dimapur	99.74	187.80	49.326	370.09	5.03

10.	Kiphire	1.00	0.26	0.068	4.92	0.13
11.	Longleng	3.33	6.62	0.365	0.05	0.00
12.	Peren	6.70	3.38	1.848	16.37	0.18
Nagaland		239.00	337.92	88.672	1069.46	11.88

Table 2 reveals the Papaya produced in few pockets of the State, In Kohima area and production 6.153 ha with yield 452440 numbers with 83710 plants. No significant cultivation in Mokochung, Tuensang, Noklak and Zunheboto, respectively. 103310 papaya productions estimated from 17.408 ha, total bearing and non-bearing in Mon was 3030; Wokha 80380 trees with total 99510 numbers in area 13.466 ha; 700 plants in Phek with area 0.039 ha with yield 3120 fruits with 370090 fruits from 49.326 ha. Dimapur the largest area 287540 plants with 1260 trees and production 4920 numbers. Total area 0.068 ha Kiphire with 0.05 ha; Longleng 9950 trees with 50 fruit; 16370 trees from Peren in area 1.848 ha and 10080 plant; the overall 88.672 ha land in Nagaland with production 1069460 and total bearing and non-bearing plants 576920 only (Shao 2007).

3. Pineapple

Table 3. Pineapple Area, Production and Number of trees

SN	Pineapple	No. of Bearing trees ('000)	No. of Non - Bearing trees ('000)	Area (ha)	Yield ('000 units)	No. of Minor trees ('000)
1.	Kohima	1.54	1.09	0.386	1.47	0.56
2.	Mokokchung	1183.85	447.82	155.7660	1878.66	13.68
3.	Tuensang	119.64	88.03	29.470	183.17	5.10
4.	Noklak	46.34	13.69	7.932	40.34	1.26
5.	Mon	286.79	190.76	89.802	249.74	3.77
6.	Wokha	2564.24	783.16	348.830	4498.56	9.27
7.	Zunheboto	863.64	163.68	114.430	1389.91	1.25
8.	Phek	762.72	221.58	97.013	1267.25	2.80
9.	Dimapur	7686.80	2941.41	478.714	8333.65	11.81
10.	Kiphire	34.69	18.41	11.102	19.50	0.63
11.	Longleng	184.82	980.66	112.147	2.41	17.28
12.	Peren	4823.58	1280.25	674.720	7098.51	5.78
Nagaland		18558.66	7130.54	2120.314	24963.16	73.18

Table 3 reveals the very sweet Pineapple produced in Nagaland with high Total Soluble Sugar content with area and production 2630 plants (bearing and non-bearing) produced 1470 with area 0.386 ha. Total area 155.766 ha in Mokokchung district, 1631760 plants, produced 1878660 fruits. Total yield 183170 units in the district of Tuensang in area 29.47 ha, total standing plant (bearing and non-bearing) 207670. Noklak 7.932 ha area produces 40340 units with total (bearing and non-bearing) 60030. Mon 89.802 ha with yield 249740 pieces from 477550.

4498560 units yield produced in Wokha in area 348.830 ha with total 3347400 in the district. Zunheboto produced 1389910 units from 1027320 with area 114.430 ha. About 1267250 units from Phek, total 984300 plants in area 97.013 ha. Dimapur area 478.714 ha, produced highest yield of 8333650 units from 10628210 plants; Kiphire 19500 units from area 11.102 ha, with 53100 plants; Longleng production 2410 units in area 112.147 ha with total 1165480 plants. Peren in 674.720 ha, yield 7098510 only, total 6103830 plants. The state produced 24963160 units from area 2120.314 ha, the total standing plant 18558660 (Shao and Tu 1995).

4. Banana

Table 4 reveals total 41830 banana plants (bearing and non-bearing) produced 196490 units of banana in area 57.71 ha, an area 62.74 ha in Mokokchung with 153590 plants and production 85500 units. Total yield 115430 bunch in Tuensang in 150.76 ha area (bearing and non-bearing 252950). Noklak 14850 units in 15.62 ha with total were 26410. Mon area 7.19 ha with yields 11390 units of 216470 plants. Wokha yield of 310450 units in 420.54 ha with 660230 numbers. Zunheboto produced 63260 units from 581490 plants total area 19.27 ha; 137740 units in Phek with 300270 unit from 169.60 ha. Dimapur area 373.46 ha produced 34618 units from 692220; Kiphire 120310 units from area 121.98 ha from 258750 plants, from Longleng 13700 units in 14.81 ha with 22680 plants; Peren being largest area 577.51 ha of yield 541070 from 98138; the State 2356360 units in area of 2229.007 ha with 4797040 plants (Joel 2019).

Table 4. Banana Area, Production and Number of trees

SN	Banana	No. of Bearing trees ('000)	No. of Non- Bearing trees ('000)	Area (ha)	Yield ('000 bunch)	No. of Minor trees ('000)
1.	Kohima	206.49	435.34	57.780	196.49	2.79
2.	Mokokchung	92.33	61.26	62.744	85.50	19.36
3.	Tuensang	117.30	135.65	150.836	115.43	10.38
4.	Noklak	16.36	10.05	15.062	14.85	2.79
5.	Mon	138.43	78.04	71.991	111.39	4.75
6.	Wokha	317.37	342.86	420.539	310.45	25.34
7.	Zunheboto	337.95	243.54	192.696	363.26	17.97
8.	Phek	165.81	134.46	169.601	137.74	11.25
9.	Dimapur	305.91	386.31	373.457	346.18	17.82
10.	Kiphire	155.71	103.04	121.980	120.31	5.32
11.	Longleng	11.34	11.34	14.809	13.70	0.90
12.	Peren	569.39	420.77	577.512	541.07	5.14
	Nagaland	2434.39	2362.65	2229.007	2356.36	123.80

5. Passion fruit

Table 5 reveals the passion fruit in Kohima 1.623 ha with 23390 plants with 75.77 ton. Mokokchung area 0.923 ha with 13.84 tons from 6920 plants; no significant area or production of passion fruit were found in Tuensang, Mon, Phek, Longleng and Peren. Noklak 8.874 ha having 147.91 tons from 25730 plants. Wokha 10.413 ha of 147.91 tons from 23930 plants; 280.01 tons from 32.50 ha with 144160 plant in Dimapur. 2.063 ha having 2.60

tons from 258000 plants with 0.75 tons in Kiphire from area 0.542 ha and from 6800 plants. The state produced 574.58 tons from area 56.947 ha with 227380 plants (Alam, Suny, and Parh 2015).

Table 5. Passion fruit Area, Production and Number of trees

SN	Passion fruit	No. of Bearing trees ('000)	No. of Non - Bearing trees ('000)	Area (ha)	Yield (ton)	No. of Minor trees ('000)
1.	Kohima	14.06	9.33	1.623	75.77	0.82
2.	Mokokchung	4.61	2.31	0.923	13.84	0.55
3.	Tuensang	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
4.	Noklak	16.26	9.47	8.874	53.69	2.44
5.	Mon	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
6.	Wokha	11.21	12.72	10.413	147.91	0.45
7.	Zunheboto	103.71	40.45	32.509	280.01	3.23
8.	Phek	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
9.	Dimapur	0.45	2.13	2.063	2.60	0.30
10.	Kiphire	0.40	0.28	0.542	0.75	0.09
11.	Longleng	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
12.	Peren	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
Nagaland		150.69	76.69	56.947	574.58	7.89

6. Guava

Table 6 reveals the guava cultivation in Kohima 2.125 ha with 31620 plants at 74.40 tons. Mokokchung 7.400 ha 151.19 tons yield from 49990 plants. No significant area or production of guava was found in Tuensang, Noklak, Mon, Wokha. 40.07 tons from 0.835 ha from 10050 plants; 192.383 ha in Phek with 426.58 tons from 27340 plants (bearing and non-bearing); Dimapur 27.258 ha with 95.830 tons from 117380 plants, 59.56 tons in Kiphire from 13.108 ha from 40150 plants; 56.12 tons from 0.494 ha of 8830 plants; 1.55 tons in Peren from 0.736 ha with 2190 plants; the state 905.30 tons from 244.340 ha from 242560 plants (Boukabcha and Rebbouh 2015).

Table 6. Guava Area, Production and Number of trees

SN	Guava	No. of Bearing trees ('000)	No. of Non - Bearing trees ('000)	Area (ha)	Yield (ton)	No. of Minor trees ('000)
1.	Kohima	16.49	15.13	2.125	74.40	3.64
2.	Mokokchung	2.99	2.00	7.400	151.19	0.74
3.	Tuensang	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
4.	Noklak	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00

5.	Mon	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
6.	Wokha	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
7.	Zunheboto	6.46	3.59	0.835	40.07	1.68
8.	Phek	10.23	17.11	192.383	426.58	1.73
9.	Dimapur	26.91	90.47	27.258	95.83	2.86
10.	Kiphire	10.90	29.25	13.108	59.56	1.02
11.	Longleng	6.82	2.01	0.494	56.12	1.07
12.	Peren	1.09	1.10	0.736	1.55	0.06
Nagaland		81.90	160.66	244.340	905.30	12.80

7. Plum

Table 7 reveals the Kohima 31.336 ha with 206230 plants of 599.87 tons; Mokokchung, Noklak, Mon, Wokha and Kiphire district had no significant area and production under plum cultivation. 25.954 ha Tuensang with 721.39 tons from 110580 plants; 624.54 tons from 14.062 ha from 156720 trees. 6.825 ha in Phek with 556.08 tons 256 plants (bearing and non-bearing); Dimapur 1.224 ha with yield 1.85 ton from 2470 plant; 109.92 ton in Longleng in 1.081 ha with 6310 trees (Efron and Tibshirani 1993). No significant pears production in Peren 0.035 ha from non-bearing plants was 61; the State with 2613.64 tons from 80.482 ha from 54890 plants (bearing and non-bearing).

Table 7. Plum Area, Production and Number of trees

SN	Plum	No. of Bearing trees ('000)	No. of Non - Bearing trees ('000)	Area (ha)	Yield (ton)	No. of Minor trees ('000)
1.	Kohima	125.06	81.17	31.336	599.87	6.96
2.	Mokokchung	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
3.	Tuensang	65.12	45.46	25.954	721.39	4.97
4.	Noklak	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
5.	Mon	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
6.	Wokha	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
7.	Zunheboto	89.38	67.34	14.062	624.54	3.92
8.	Phek	30.61	35.98	6.825	556.08	5.41
9.	Dimapur	0.15	2.32	1.224	1.85	0.26
10.	Kiphire	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
11.	Longleng	3.30	3.01	1.081	109.92	0.38
12.	Peren	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
Nagaland		313.62	235.28	80.482	2613.64	21.90

8. Pears

Table 8. Pears Area, Production and Number of trees

SN	Pear	No. of Bearing trees ('000)	No. of Non - Bearing trees ('000)	Area (ha)	Yield (ton)	No. of Minor trees ('000)
1.	Kohima	9.71	4.58	7.303	472.79	2.03
2.	Mokokchung	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
3.	Tuensang	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
4.	Noklak	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
5.	Mon	27.10	12.55	28.309	1902.74	2.51
6.	Wokha	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
7.	Zunheboto	101.24	41.93	83.424	5214.62	4.32
8.	Phek	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
9.	Dimapur	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
10.	Kiphire	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
11.	Longleng	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
12.	Peren	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
	Nagaland	138.04	59.06	119.036	7590.15	8.86

Table 8 reveals the Kohima 7.303 ha with 14588 trees of 472.79 tons. No significant area or production was observed in Mokokchung, Noklak, Wokha, Phek, Dimapur, Kiphire and Peren. Mon 28.309 ha with 325.428 tons from 39650 trees; 5214.62 tons from 83.424 ha from 143170 trees; no significant pears production was observed from 0.073 ha of land from 37 trees (non-bearing and young); the state 7590.15 tons of pears from 119.036 ha from 19710 trees (Hendi 2017).

9. Apple

Table 9. Apple Area, Production and Number of trees

SN	Apple	No. of Bearing trees ('000)	No. of Non - Bearing trees ('000)	Area (ha)	Yield (ton)	No. of Minor trees ('000)
1.	Kohima	3.66	13.40	5.431	17.95	1.35
2.	Mokokchung	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
3.	Tuensang	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
4.	Noklak	4.61	4.64	1.532	7.04	0.76
5.	Mon	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00

6.	Wokha	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
7.	Zunheboto	4.48	17.52	3.956	14.03	0.53
8.	Phek	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
9.	Dimapur	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
10.	Kiphire	4.55	23.37	4.28	18.47	0.49
11.	Longleng	1.73	12.65	1.962	8.56	0.37
12.	Peren	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
Nagaland		19.03	71.59	17.709	66.04	3.51

Table 9 reveals that Apple in 5.431 ha Kohima with 17060 trees with 17.95 tons. No significant area or production from the survey in Mokokchung, Tuensang, Mon, Wokha, Phek Dimapur and Peren; 7.04 tons from 1.532 ha of 14380 trees; 14.03 tons from 3.956 ha from 22000 trees. 18.47 tons in Kiphire of 4.28 ha with 27920 trees being largest area; 8.56 tons from 1.962 ha from 14380 trees; state with 66.04 tons from 17.709 ha with 90620 trees (Efron 1990).

10. Jackfruit

Table 10. Jackfruit Area, Production and Number of trees

SN	Jackfruit	No. of Bearing trees ('000)	No. of Non - Bearing trees ('000)	Area (ha)	Yield ('000 units)	No. of Minor trees ('000)
1.	Kohima	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
2.	Mokokchung	6.54	5.48	6.426	322.23	1.01
3.	Tuensang	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
4.	Noklak	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
5.	Mon	14.77	46.40	47.753	132.46	3.69
6.	Wokha	6.38	12.63	15.638	54.43	1.16
7.	Zunheboto	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
8.	Phek	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
9.	Dimapur	36.96	158.93	131.356	1065.33	8.73
10.	Kiphire	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
11.	Longleng	1.35	1.70	1.278	113.53	0.27
12.	Peren	4.86	22.11	21.406	51.61	1.01
Nagaland		70.86	247.25	223.856	1739.59	15.87

Table 10 reveals that the jackfruits production or area was observed in Mokokchung 6.426 ha with 12020 trees produced 322230 units. No significant area and production of jackfruit was found from Kohima, Tuensang, Noklak, Zunheboto, Phek, Kiphire; Mon 47.753 ha with 132460 units from 61170 trees. 53430 units in Wokha from 15.638 ha with 19010 trees; Dimapur 131.356 ha with 1065330 units from 195880 trees being largest producing area; Longleng 113530 units from 1.278 ha with 3050 trees; Peren 21.406 ha with 51610 units from 26980 trees. The state 1739590 units of 223.856 ha with 318110 trees (Efron 1979).

11. Litchi

Table 11 reveals the total litchi 29950 plants (bearing and non-bearing) from 113710 bunches from 1.481 ha; 46.325 ha Mokokchung having 108560 plants from 323370 bunches of fruit. No significant area or production of litchi was observed in Tuensang, Noklak, Zunheboto, Kiphire district. Mon 0.745 ha with yield of 21760 bunches from 8790 plants; yield of 37110 bunch in Wokha from 3.189 ha with 21070 plant. 13420 bunch in Phek with 8360 plant from 0.383 ha; Dimapur 278.210 ha produced highest yield 11063 bunch from 197580 plants. Longleng 78690 bunch from 1.409 ha with 24310 plants. Peren 4.843 ha of 10030 bunches from 12560 plants. The state produced 11661340 bunches from 336.583 ha from 411190 plants (Dutta 2010).

Table 11. Litchi Area, Production and Number of trees

SN	Litchi	No. of Bearing trees ('000)	No. of Non - Bearing trees ('000)	Area (ha)	Yield ('000 bunch)	No. of Minor trees ('000)
1.	Kohima	19.56	10.39	1.481	113.71	0.58
2.	Mokokchung	116.09	81.49	278.210	11063.25	13.22
3.	Tuensang	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
4.	Noklak	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
5.	Mon	6.11	2.68	0.745	21.76	0.63
6.	Wokha	12.58	8.49	3.189	37.11	1.25
7.	Zunheboto	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
8.	Phek	5.09	3.27	0.383	13.42	0.56
9.	Dimapur	58.19	50.37	46.324	323.37	8.27
10.	Kiphire	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
11.	Longleng	15.43	8.88	1.409	78.69	0.52
12.	Peren	5.14	7.42	4.843	10.03	1.59
Nagaland		238.19	173.00	33.658	11661.34	26.61

12. Pomegranate

Table 12 reveals the pomegranate cultivation Kohima 4.036 ha with 39080 trees with 233.52 tons. No significant area or production was observed for pomegranate in Mokokchung, Mon, Zunheboto, Kiphire Longleng and Peren. 21.455 ha in Tuensang with 375.63 tons from 101870 trees. 85.52 tons from 1.465 ha in Noklak from 13800 trees; Wokha 0.056 ha with 0.84 tons with 670 trees; no significant production was recorded from 2.190 ha in Phek with 90.23 tons with 13890 trees (bearing and non-bearing); Dimapur 0.442 ha with 3.16 tons from 3160 trees. The state produced 788.90 tons from 29.644 ha from 172470 trees (Efron 1981).

Table 12. Pomegranate Area, Production and Number of trees

SN	Pomegranate	No. of Bearing trees ('000)	No. of Non - Bearing trees ('000)	Area (ha)	Yield (ton)	No. of Minor trees ('000)
1.	Kohima	28.96	10.12	4.036	233.52	1.64
2.	Mokokchung	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
3.	Tuensang	44.48	57.38	21.455	375.63	9.59
4.	Noklak	10.20	3.60	1.465	85.52	0.66
5.	Mon	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
6.	Wokha	0.34	0.34	0.056	0.84	0.14
7.	Zunheboto	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
8.	Phek	9.34	4.55	2.190	90.23	0.80
9.	Dimapur	1.71	1.45	0.442	3.16	0.88
10.	Kiphire	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
11.	Longleng	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
12.	Peren	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
Nagaland		95.03	77.44	29.644	788.90	13.72

13. Kiwi**Table 13. Kiwi Area, Production and Numbers of tree**

SN	Kiwi	No. of Bearing trees ('000)	No. of Non - Bearing trees ('000)	Area (ha)	Yield (ton)	No. of Minor trees ('000)
1.	Kohima	24.09	49.91	3.554	169.05	2.31
2.	Mokokchung	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
3.	Tuensang	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
4.	Noklak	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
5.	Mon	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
6.	Wokha	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
7.	Zunheboto	100.11	279.10	16.589	686.96	11.90
8.	Phek	59.17	117.80	9.591	496.74	4.75

9.	Dimapur	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
10.	Kiphire	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
11.	Longleng	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
12.	Peren	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
Nagaland		183.37	446.82	29.734	1352.75	18.96

Table 13 reveals the kiwi in Kohima 3.544 ha with 74000 plants and 169.05 tons. No significant area or production of kiwi was observed in Mokokchung, Tuensang, Noklak, Mon, Wokha, Dimapur, Kiphire, Longleng and Peren; 686.96 tons from 16.589 ha from 379210 plants; Zunheboto being largest area and production; 9.591 ha in Phek with 496.74 tons with 176970 plants (bearing and non-bearing); the state 1352.75 tons of 29.734 ha with 630190 plants (Joel 2019).

14. Others fruits (Lemon, Peach, Grapes, Mango, Parkia, Gooseberry, Strawberry etc;)

Table 14. Others Area, Production and Number of trees

SN	Other	No. of Bearing trees ('000)	No. of Non - Bearing trees ('000)	Area (ha)	Yield (ton)	No. of Minor trees ('000)
1.	Kohima	41.02	39.35	8.252	246.63	3.46
2.	Mokokchung	59.98	26.12	104.732	5423.99	14.72
3.	Tuensang	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
4.	Noklak	4.91	3.25	1.608	29.60	0.71
5.	Mon	15.88	20.05	10.459	68.21	1.98
6.	Wokha	10.86	8.32	8.939	42.08	3.21
7.	Zunheboto	8.41	9.80	9.498	28.14	2.68
8.	Phek	14.47	8.74	6.149	91.02	2.81
9.	Dimapur	231.08	468.29	331.760	601.75	18.43
10.	Kiphire	0.00	0.00	0.000	0.00	0.00
11.	Longleng	6.80	6.20	4.015	39.25	1.34
12.	Peren	49.88	76.53	31.420	251.64	8.30
Nagaland		443.28	666.66	516.832	6822.31	57.65

Table 14 reveals the other fruits cultivation in Kohima 8.252 ha with 80370 plants at 246.63 ton. Mokokchung 104.732 ha at 5423.99 ton with 86100 plants; no significant area or production of other fruits was observed in Tuensang, Kiphire. Noklak district produces 29.60 tons in 1.608 ha with 15925 plants. Mon 10.459 ha with 68.21 ton 35930 plants; Wokha 8.939 ha of 42.08 ton with 19180 trees; 28.14 ton from 9.498 ha from 18210 plants; 6.149 ha in Phek with 91.02 ton with 23210 plants (bearing and non-bearing); Dimapur 331.760 ha with

601.75 ton from 699370 plants; 39.25 ton from 4.015 ha from 13000 plants; 251.64 ton in Peren from 31.420 ha with 126410 plants. The state produced 6822.31 ton from 516.832 ha (Boukabcha and Rebbouh 2015).

Table 15. Socio economic profile of fruit growers

S N	District	Occupation		Type of farming		Mode of marketing			
		Primary	Secondary	Solo	Mixed	Directly from field	Contract	Directly to market	Wholesaler
1.	Kohima	237	48	181	104	170	5	65	45
2.	Makokchung	251	54	194	110	165	7	80	53
3.	Tuensang	61	13	47	28	45	7	12	10
4.	Noklak	118	25	91	52	85	8	30	20
5.	Mon	206	43	158	91	134	20	50	45
6.	Wokha	202	43	156	89	140	17	60	28
7.	Zunheboto	109	23	84	48	72	10	35	15
8.	Phek	159	33	122	69	108	8	45	31
9.	Dimapur	164	34	126	72	107	7	55	29
10.	Kiphire	84	18	65	38	60	6	25	11
11.	Longleng	128	27	99	56	86	9	35	25
12.	Peren	98	22	76	44	65	5	30	20
Nagaland		1817	383	1399	801	1237	109	522	332

Table 15 reveals that 82.59 per cent of the respondents feels farming is primary occupation, while 17.41 per cent feel and involved in other activities. While to fruit marketing, the most people were found selling goods straight from the field with 56.23 per cent. 23.73 per cent were detected peddling their wares on the street. 15.01 per cent sell their produce to wholesalers, only 4.95 per cent favoured contract selling. 36.41 per cent favoured mixed farming, while the remaining 63.59 per cent, selected solo fruit crop farming (Lahiri 2003).

Table 16. Constraints faced by respondents

SN	District	Transportation	Climate	Accessibility To market	Manpower	Machineries	All
1.	Kohima	120	45	65	96	145	5
2.	Makokchung	160	6	180	140	155	3
3.	Tuensang	21	5	2	12	190	7
4.	Noklak	156	10	8	14	37	4
5.	Mon	156	15	190	4	210	0
6.	Wokha	90	2	87	220	175	6
7.	Zunheboto	175	4	180	7	163	9
8.	Phek	160	8	176	70	185	35
9.	Dimapur	65	5	60	50	75	3
10.	Kiphire	26	100	20	85	3	0
11.	Longleng	110	0	120	110	120	38
12.	Peren	15	2	10	0	15	0
Nagaland		1254	202	1098	808	1473	110

The table 16 below displays the various limitations based on the number of responders in each district. The largest barrier for fruit production and harvesting, according to 66.95 per cent of respondents, was lack of adequate machinery and tools. Next, 57.00 per cent of total respondents recognised transportation as an issue, and 49.90 per cent of respondents perceived market accessibility or market-related constraints as difficult. Manpower shortages were cited as a restriction by 36.73 per cent of respondents.

In Nagaland, the coefficient of variation for orange production as a significant crop was 1.604 percent and 1.606 per cent in bootstrap and jackknife resampling method and the number of bearing fruit trees of orange was 1.725 per cent and 1.762 per cent, which is obtained after performing bootstrap and jackknife resampling method (table 17). The coefficient of variation for papaya was determined to be 2.208 per cent and 2.233 per cent in bootstrap and jackknife resampling method for number of bearing trees and 2.492 per cent and 2.517 per cent in bootstrap and jackknife resampling for yearly production (table 18).

Pineapple was found to have a CV of Annual yield was 2.967 per cent and 3.100 per cent obtained from bootstrap and jackknife resampling. The CV value obtained after performing bootstrap and jackknife for number of bearing trees for Pineapple was 3.195 per cent and 3.614 per cent (table 19), and banana yield had a same CV from both the resampling method of 9.268 percent and bearing tree had a CV of 9.313 per cent and 9.447 per cent from bootstrap and jackknife (table 20). The yield of passion fruit varied by 3.551 per cent and 3.839 per cent in bootstrap and jackknife, the number of yielding trees varied by 3.283 per cent and 3.250 per cent from bootstrap and jackknife resampling method (table 21).

Guava production varied by 2.834 per cent, 2.972 per cent in bootstrap and jackknife method, respectively and number of yielding trees varied by 2.585 per cent in jackknife and 2.556 per cent in case of bootstrap resampling method (table 22). In Nagaland, the coefficient of variation for plum yield was 2.883 per cent both in bootstrap and jackknife, while the number of bearing trees was 2.948 per cent and 2.852 per cent in jackknife and bootstrap resampling method respectively (table 23). Pears had a yield variation of 3.589 per cent obtained from bootstrap resampling and 3.576 per cent in jackknife method, whereas bearing trees had a variety of 3.470 per cent for bootstrap and 3.496 per cent for jackknife (table 24).

Apples had a yield variation of 3.705 per cent for bootstrap and 3.644 per cent for jackknife, whereas bearing trees had a variation of 3.862 per cent and 3.824 per cent for bootstrap and jackknife respectively (table 25). The number of bearing trees in jackfruit had a CV of 2.259 per cent for bootstrap and 2.252 per cent for jackknife, whereas the yield variation was 4.073 per cent and 4.627 per cent for bootstrap and jackknife, respectively (table 26). Litchi's yield varied by 3.914821 per cent in case of bootstrap and 4.254 per cent in jackknife in the state and the number of bearing trees varied by 2.474 per cent in both bootstrap and jackknife (table 27).

Pomegranate had a yield CV of 2.891 per cent in bootstrap as well as jackknife and a number of bearing trees CV of approx.2.906 per cent in both of the resampling method (table 28); the yield of kiwis varied by 3.052 per cent and the number of bearing trees varied by 3.153 per cent for both bootstrap and jackknife (table 29). The yield of other varied by 2.788 per cent and the number of bearing trees varied by 1.798 per cent (Table 30) for both bootstrap and jackknife, respectively.

Table 17. Bootstrap and jackknife estimation of yield and bearing trees of orange

ORANGE	METHOD	EST. CV	VARIANC E	SE	BIAS	SD	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL
BEARING	ORIGIN	1.762918					
	BOOTST	1.725372	0.025819	0.1620154	-0.038	0.16068	1.40782- 2.04292
	JACKKN	1.761673	0.01279	0.1701622	-0.033	0.11313	1.428155-2.095191
YIELD	ORIGIN	1.606387					
	BOOTST	1.60429	0.019563	0.1419485	0.0021	0.13987	1.326071-1.882509
	JACKKN	1.605885	0.010729	0.1398842	0.0081	0.10358	1.331712-1.880057

Table 18. Bootstrap and jackknife estimation of yield and bearing trees of papaya

PAPAYA	METHOD	EST. CV	VARIANCE	SE	BIAS	SD	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL
BEARING	ORIGIN	2.22151					
	BOOTST	2.208337	0.075561	0.2730827	0.0088	0.274884	1.673095-2.743579
	JACKKN	2.232644	0.1173991	0.342636	-0.0153	0.342636	1.64799-2.817297
YIELD	ORIGIN	2.50545					
	BOOTST	2.492102	0.103415	0.3169036	-0.0134	0.321582	1.863618-3.120585
	JACKKN	2.516629	0.290629	0.348655	-0.0211	0.539101	1.833265-3.199952

Table 19. Bootstrap and jackknife estimation of yield and bearing trees of pineapple

PINEAPPLE	METHOD	EST. CV	VARIANCE	SE	BIAS	SD	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL
BEARING	ORIGIN	3.614249					
	BOOTST	3.194719	0.526716	0.71769	-0.4195	0.72575	2.659465-3.729949
	JACKKN	3.61425	0.372358	1.23467	-0.8242	0.61021	1.200934-6.040836
YIELD	ORIGIN	3.09077					
	BOOTST	2.96734	0.197392	0.4402857	-0.1235	0.55252	2.104375-3.830295
	JACKKN	3.10016	0.30528	0.5293005	-0.165	0.44429	2.062735-4.137593

Table 20. Bootstrap and jackknife estimation of yield and bearing trees of banana

BANANA	METHOD	ESTIMATE D CV	VARIANCE	SE	BIAS	SD	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL
BEARING	ORIGINA	9.449584					
	BOOTSTR	9.312891	0.052306	0.70874	0.13670	0.072323	7.923766-10.70201
	JACKKNI	9.447002	0.072412	0.73743	0.07592	0.085095	8.00164-1.089237
YIELD	ORIGINA	9.398693					
	BOOTSTR	9.268459	0.053278	0.7213	-0.13023	0.729918	7.854671-10.68225
	JACKKNI	9.268459	0.0643602	0.76211	0.07693	0.80225	7.903818-10.89129

Table 21. Bootstrap and jackknife estimation of yield and bearing trees of passion fruit

PASSION	METHOD	ESTIMATE D CV	VARIANCE	SE	BIAS	SD	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL
BEARING	ORIGINA	3.249393					
	BOOTSTR	3.283276	0.2687627	0.5075607	0.033884	0.51842	2.288457-4.278098
	JACKKNI	3.250127	0.208998	0.4952749	0.04744	0.45716	2.279388-4.220866
YIELD	ORIGINA	3.834594					
	BOOTSTR	3.551349	0.4958489	0.6965752	-0.28324	0.70417	2.186062-4.916637
	JACKKNI	3.839702	0.4549371	1.101466	-0.64827	0.67449	1.680828-5.998575

Table 22. Bootstrap and jackknife estimation of yield and bearing trees of guava

GUAVA	METHOD	ESTIMATE D CV	VARIANCE	SE	BIAS	SD	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL
BEARING	ORIGINA	2.577813					
	BOOTSTR	2.556396	0.2306565	0.4777984	-0.13481	0.48027	1.897117-3.770087
	JACKKNI	2.584903	1.372231	0.6657895	-0.25645	1.1714	1.667804-4.277699

YIELD	ORIGINA	2.96841					
	BOOTSTR	2.833602	0.2306565	0.4777984	-0.13481	0.48027	1.897117-3.770087
	JACKKNI	2.972752	1.372231	0.6657895	-0.25645	1.1714	1.667804-4.277699

Table 23. Bootstrap and jackknife estimation of yield and bearing trees of plum

PLUM	METHOD	ESTIMATE D CV	VARIAN CE	SE	BIAS	SD	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL
BEARING	ORIGINA	2.936196					
	BOOTSTR	2.85234	0.1777444	0.4159613	-0.08386	0.42161	2.037056-3.667624
	JACKKNI	2.948132	0.5994597	0.4835657	-0.1213	0.77425	2.000343-3.895921
YIELD	ORIGINA	2.867129					
	BOOTSTR	2.870934	0.1531854	0.3927313	0.0038	0.39139	2.10118-3.640687
	JACKKNI	2.883306	0.2254029	0.397264	0.00807	0.47477	2.104668-3.661943

Table 24. Bootstrap and jackknife estimation of yield and bearing trees of pear

PEAR	METHOD	ESTIMATE D CV	VARIAN CE	SE	BIAS	SD	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL
BEARING	ORIGINA	3.494255					
	BOOTSTR	3.47068	0.3469261	0.6012856	-0.02358	0.58901	2.292161-4.6492
	JACKKNI	3.496383	0.2417423	0.6064773	-0.05697	0.49167	2.307687-4.685079
YIELD	ORIGINA	3.577745					
	BOOTSTR	3.588882	0.3740505	0.6237221	0.01114	0.61161	2.366387-4.811378
	JACKKNI	3.575538	0.2432524	0.5914303	0.024123	0.49321	2.416335-4.734741

Table 25. Bootstrap and jackknife estimation of yield and bearing trees of apple

APPLE	METHOD	ESTIMATE D CV	VARIAN CE	SE	BIAS	SD	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL
BEARING	ORIGINA	3.82751					
	BOOTSTR	3.861698	0.501456	0.705255	0.034189	0.708136	2.479398-5.243998
	JACKKNI	3.824647	0.187079	0.6840938	0.04766	0.432526	2.483823-5.165471
YIELD	ORIGINA	3.642844					
	BOOTSTR	3.705306	0.4374353	0.6596517	0.06246	0.661389	2.412388-4.998223
	JACKKNI	3.643864	0.2429175	0.6497262	0.082753	0.492867	2.3704-4.917327

Table 26. Bootstrap and jackknife estimation of yield and bearing trees of jackfruit

JACKFRUIT	METHOD	ESTIMATE D CV	VARIAN CE	SE	BIAS	SD	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL
BEARING	ORIGINA	2.258538					
	BOOTSTR	2.259869	0.0771707	0.2762503	0.001331	0.27780	1.718419-2.80132
	JACKKNI	2.251952	0.0569386	0.2827083	0.011677	0.23862	1.697844-2.806061
YIELD	ORIGINA	4.677281					
	BOOTSTR	4.073071	0.8503254	0.9302195	-0.64209	0.92213	2.249841-5.896301
	JACKKNI	4.62742	7.451193	1.511205	-1.2718	2.72968	1.665457-7.589382

Table 27. Bootstrap and jackknife estimation of yield and bearing trees of litchi

LITCHI	METHOD	ESTIMATE D CV	VARIAN CE	SE	BIAS	SD	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL
BEARING	ORIGINA	2.466739					
	BOOTSTR	2.442571	0.0738170	0.2721967	-0.24168	0.271693	1.909065-2.976077
	JACKKNI	2.474781	0.0881352	0.2658712	0.008077	0.296876	1.953674-2.995889
YIELD	ORIGINA	4.220313					
	BOOTSTR	3.914821	0.5619171	0.7374979	-0.30550	0.749611	2.469325-5.360317
	JACKKNI	4.254708	3.311479	0.967704	-0.52076	1.819747	2.358008-6.151408

Table 28. Bootstrap and jackknife estimation of yield and bearing trees of pomegranate

POMEGRANATE	METHOD	ESTIMATE D CV	VARIAN CE	SE	BIAS	SD	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL
BEARING	ORIGINA	2.860932					
	BOOTSTR	2.906984	0.1884121	0.4333413	0.046052	0.434065	2.057635-3.756333
	JACKKNI	2.887026	0.3438107	0.4202273	0.058398	0.586354	2.06338-3.710671
YIELD	ORIGINA	2.835811					
	BOOTSTR	2.891427	0.2008777	0.4467639	0.055616	0.448194	2.015769-3.767084
	JACKKNI	2.860836	0.3541275	0.4281801	0.672518	0.59508	2.021604-3.700069

Table 29. Bootstrap and jackknife estimation of yield and bearing trees of kiwi

KIWI	METHOD	ESTIMATE D CV	VARIAN CE	SE	BIAS	SD	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL
BEARING	ORIGINA	3.123898					
	BOOTSTR	3.152985	0.2369612	0.4906917	0.029087	0.486787	2.191229-4.114741
	JACKKNI	3.121841	0.1434204	0.466859	0.041074	0.378709	2.206797-4.0368847
YIELD	ORIGINA	3.019498					
	BOOTSTR	3.052136	0.2200284	0.4698862	0.032638	0.469072	2.131159-3.973113
	JACKKNI	3.018502	0.1686302	0.45028	0.040032	0.410646	2.135953-3.901051

Table 30. Bootstrap and jackknife estimation of yield and bearing trees of others

OTHERS	METHOD	ESTIMATE D CV	VARIAN CE	SE	BIAS	SD	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL
BEARING	ORIGINA	3.123898					
	BOOTSTR	3.152985	0.2369612	0.4906917	0.029087	0.486787	2.191229-4.114741
	JACKKNI	3.121841	0.1434204	0.466859	0.041074	0.378709	2.206797-4.0368847
YIELD	ORIGINA	3.019498					
	BOOTSTR	3.052136	0.2200284	0.4698862	0.032638	0.469072	2.131159-3.973113
	JACKKNI	3.018502	0.1686302	0.45028	0.040032	0.410646	2.135953-3.901051

CONCLUSIONS

The main conclusion can be drawn from 13 fruit crop viz; Orange, Papaya, Pineapple, Banana, Passion fruit, Guava, Plum, Pear, Apple, Jackfruit, Litchi, Pomegranate and Kiwi were grown as major fruit crop; out of that the largest area is covered by orange cultivation followed by banana cultivation and apple had the lowest area under cultivation Mixed farming is preferred, while solo farming was favoured, so single-type farming is easier to manage the orchard-based farming or single-fruit crop plantation based farming is more popular in Nagaland. The lack of suitable machinery and tools were identified as a major barrier by the majority fruit growers, followed by

transportations accessibility or market-related limits as a problem. The result of running bootstrap and jackknife resampling method from the original data set for CV estimation of fruit crop yield and bearing fruit trees show a large increased in accuracy.

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